

Mapping and forecasting of fall armyworm pest distribution in East Africa using climate information

Nasson Ntwari*, Rosita Yocgo, Pancras Ndokoye, Desire Kagabo

African Institute for Mathematical Sciences, Rwanda

*Email: nasson.ntwari@aims.ac.rw

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Abstract

We assessed climate variables that influence a serious crop pest distribution and mapped its current suitable habitats in eastern Africa using Species Distribution Models (SDMs) along with the most recent occurrence data set of the pest and high-resolution climate data of 30 seconds. We further predicted its future suitable habitat using the highest and the lowest climate-sensitive Global Circulation Models from the new CMIP6 family of models and for three climate scenarios. We used FAW occurrence coordinates, current climate data, and predicted potential future scenarios and one of the high-performing and accurate SDMs, MaxEnt. We evaluated the MaxEnt model performance and determined climate variables that influence FAW distribution in East Africa. We mapped FAW's current suitable habitat and predicted its potential future suitable habitats and spread using three future climate scenarios (optimistic, moderate, and pessimistic climate scenarios). The maxent model was able to project the current suitable habitats of FAW, with a high Area Under the Curve value of 0.942. Annual precipitation and annual mean temperature were the main contributors to the model's performance. Our study also revealed that currently, the northern part of our study area has less suitable habitats for FAW. These habitats were also found to expand over the study period compared to other eastern African regions. While this was true with both GCMs, CanEMS5 overprojected these habitats in comparison to INM-CM5-0. Findings provide a better insight into how FAW is likely to spread in such resource-constrained regions like eastern Africa. This would further help to sharpen decision-making. Control and monitoring measures should be adopted to prevent the spread and excess damage of the FAW pest in the eastern Africa region.

Keywords: Climate change, Maxent, Shared Socioeconomic-Pathways, Species Distribution Models

Introduction

The impact of climate change on the agricultural sector is a global concern. Unfavorable climates exacerbate the interaction between plants, pathogens, and pests, as they inform the life cycle of pathogens and pests, the ability to cause disease, including the colonization of new environments and hosts. This also applies to host plants. Abiotic factors such as extreme temperatures, precipitation, wind, and drought further render plants more vulnerable to pests and pathogens. For example, Agrios (2005) positioned temperature and moisture as significant environmental factors that affect the occurrence and development of various infectious plant diseases. With an unprecedented future climate that will be characterized by increased warming, even under prescribed climate mitigation scenarios, there is a need to continuously understand how climate change will impact plant pathogen/pest dynamics. Predicting where the latter will exist is the first important step in putting in place adequate early preparedness strategies. However, there has been a lack of extensive research on the effects of climate change on plant diseases and how to manage these diseases in a changing climate, few evaluations exist for certain countries, regions, crops, and specific pathogens that have a notable impact on food security and nutrition, (Das et al., 2016). This study focuses on therefore on *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Fall armyworm - FAW) pest which has recently become a concern in East Africa, especially in the agriculture sector. FAW, named the hungry caterpillar, is a moth that originates from the Americas (Day et al., 2017). FAW caterpillars are known to be serious pests of cereals and other grasses. The pest is postulated to have the ability to feed on 186 plant species, many of which are important staple crops (Early et al., 2018). Maize is the main crop affected by FAW. However, its polyphagous ability put at risk other important food crops such as rice, sorghum, sugarcane, beet, tomato, potato, cotton, and pasture grass (Early et al., 2018; Uzayisenga et al., 2018). FAW can cause extreme damage in plants, with a yield of up to 73% reported (Hruska & Gould, 1997). According to Baudron et al. (2019), a 54% infestation of maize by FAW could translate to eventual yield losses of about 12%. This in turn has caused huge losses to governments, for example, about 40% of maize yield is lost in Honduras and 72% in Argentina due to FAW (Murúa et al., 2006; Wyckhuys & O'Neil, 2006).

FAW was first observed on the African continent in Western Africa (Nigeria, São Tomé, Benin, and Togo) in 2016. It then quickly spread to other countries, including Eastern African countries (Goergen et al., 2016). Its rapid spread and colonization success has been attributed to its ability to migrate over long distances, infest various crops, and reproduce continuously in areas with

suitable climate conditions (Day et al., 2017; Huesing et al., 2018). Maize, the most-grown crop on the African continent and a staple of around half of the African population remains the most affected crop (Day et al., 2017). Yield damages of about 20% to 50%, which amounts to 2.5 to 6 billion annually have been reported in Africa. This is especially true in the absence of control measures. According to Goergen et al. (2016), most FAW damage to maize occurs in tropical regions with optimal conditions that allow continuous reproduction. In Kenya, an estimated 1 million tonnes of the country's annual maize crop are destroyed by the pest each year (De Groote et al., 2020). By 2018, FAW had ravaged around 15,699 hectares of farmland, a quarter of the country's total area of 63,499 hectares of maize plantations in Rwanda (Hanyurwimfura et al., 2018). In 2017, national estimates of the mean loss of maize in Zambia were 40% and 45% in Ghana (Day et al., 2017). Zimbabwe's crop losses to FAW were estimated at 11.6% in 2018 (Baudron et al., 2019). Overall, in 2017, already infested African countries losses were estimated to be approximately \$13 383 million (Day et al., 2017). In August 2017, 28 African countries had already observed and confirmed the presence of FAW (Day et al., 2017), currently, about 44 African countries have reported the presence of FAW (Prasanna et al., 2018; Rwomushana, 2019). Climatic conditions such as temperature, and precipitation can directly influence insect invasion, distribution, and spread (Bale et al., 2002). Species Distribution Models (SDMs) and mapping tools have been used to assess climate factors that affect FAW's distribution. Early et al. (2018) utilized an ensemble of SDMs to forecast FAW global extent invasion under the current climatic scenario while Cokola et al. (2020) used MaxEnt to infer bioclimatic regions and climate variables that influence FAW's distribution in South Kivu, eastern Democratic Republic of Congo. Zacarias (2020) and Ramasamy (2022) mapped the current FAW suitable habitat and forecasted its potential future suitable habitat using SDMs. Such kinds of studies need to be downscaled to specific regions especially regions that have already been invaded by the FAW pest. Niassy et al. (2021) studied the impact of rainfall patterns on FAW incidence in East Africa. An ongoing study (Yocgo et al., unpublished). The need for more localized studies to sharpen decision-making, using new datasets therefore informed the need to also investigate in more detail, at the regional scale and with different GCMs. Eastern Africa was selected as a region of choice in this paper given the most recent occurrences of the pests in the region. The objective of this study is therefore to assess climate variables that influence FAW distribution in eastern Africa and predict its current and future suitable habitat in the region using Maxent and newly developed climate models from

the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project 6 (CMIP6). Given that different models have been shown to have different sensitivities to climate change, we compared outputs from the most sensitive model CanEMS5, and the least sensitive INM-CM5-0.

Material and methods

Description of the study area

Our study is limited to eleven countries that cover the eastern African region (Chamberlin, 2018) including Tanzania, Burundi, Rwanda, Uganda, Kenya, Somalia, Ethiopia, Djibouti, Eritrea, South Sudan, and Sudan. The region's highest altitude point is 5,895 meters above sea level on the peak of Mount Kilimanjaro (Tanzania) and the lowest point is 153 meters below sea level at the bottom of the lake Assal in Djibouti (Chamberlin, 2018). The region's complex topography, which is different from the rest of Africa, is characterized by a coastal plain in the east and mostly highlands from the north to south detached between Kenya and Ethiopia highlands by a narrow gap called the Turkana gap. This landscape greatly affects low-level atmospheric circulation and moisture movement, creating a wide variety of climatic conditions, which in turn influences a variety of vegetation landscapes, biodiversity, and human activities (Chamberlin, 2018; Yang et al., 2015). The recorded coolest place in East Africa is at Mount Kilimanjaro summit with an annual mean temperature of -7.1°C and the hottest place is at Dallol, Afar Depression (North Ethiopia) with an annual temperature of 34.6°C . The peak solar radiation ($292 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) is found in northern Somalia and the lowest ($183 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) is found in Uganda near Mt. Ruwenzori (Chamberlin, 2018).

Occurrence data

The occurrence data was obtained from the Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International (CABI; (<https://www.cabidigitallibrary.org/doi/10.1079/cabicompndium.29810>)) and the Hand in Hand platform (<https://data.apps.fao.org/>) a geospatial data repository of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations. Additionally, FAW occurrence data were obtained from literature in a study carried out by Niassy et al. (2021) which covered particularly Ethiopia, Kenya, Uganda, Tanzania, Rwanda, and Burundi. After data cleaning (removing duplicates) and cropping to the East African extent specifically, our final dataset comprised 2152 points covering the period 2017 to 2021. Data cleaning was carried out in Rstudio 4.1.3 version, a free statistical programming language.

Climate data

The climatic data used in this study was downloaded from WorldClim (<https://worldclim.org/data/index.html>), a database of historical (near current) and future gridded

weather and climate data. These data sets have been used in various SDM studies including (Baloch et al., 2020; Çoban et al., 2020; Cokola et al., 2020; Ramasamy et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2019). In our study, we used all 19 bioclimatic variables (

Code	Bioclimatic variables	Unit
Bio1	Annual Mean Temperature	°C
Bio2	Mean diurnal range (mean of monthly (max temp-min temp))	°C
Bio3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (*100)	-
Bio4	Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation *100)	C of V
Bio5	Max Temperature of the Warmest Month	°C
Bio6	Min Temperature of the Coldest Month	°C
Bio7	Temperature Annual Range (BIO5-BIO6)	°C
Bio 8	Mean Temperature of the Wettest Quarter	°C
Bio 9	Mean Temperature of the Driest Quarter	°C
Bio 10	The mean temperature of the warmest quarter	°C
Bio 11	The mean temperature of the coldest quarter	°C
Bio 12	Annual precipitation	mm
Bio 13	Precipitation of the wettest month	mm
Bio 14	Precipitation of the driest month	mm
Bio 15	Precipitation seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)	
Bio 16	Precipitation of the wettest quarter	mm
Bio 17	Precipitation of the driest quarter	mm
Bio 18	Precipitation of the warmest quarter	mm
Bio 19	Precipitation of the coldest quarter	mm

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Table 1. Bioclimatic variables derived from Worldclim were used to assess the suitable habitat of the FAW in the eastern Africa region.

Code	Bioclimatic variables	Unit
Bio1	Annual Mean Temperature	°C
Bio2	Mean diurnal range (mean of monthly (max temp-min temp))	°C
Bio3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (*100)	-

Bio4	Temperature Seasonality (standard deviation *100)	C of V
Bio5	Max Temperature of the Warmest Month	°C
Bio6	Min Temperature of the Coldest Month	°C
Bio7	Temperature Annual Range (BIO5-BIO6)	°C
Bio 8	Mean Temperature of the Wettest Quarter	°C
Bio 9	Mean Temperature of the Driest Quarter	°C
Bio 10	The mean temperature of the warmest quarter	°C
Bio 11	The mean temperature of the coldest quarter	°C
Bio 12	Annual precipitation	mm
Bio 13	Precipitation of the wettest month	mm
Bio 14	Precipitation of the driest month	mm
Bio 15	Precipitation seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)	
Bio 16	Precipitation of the wettest quarter	mm
Bio 17	Precipitation of the driest quarter	mm
Bio 18	Precipitation of the warmest quarter	mm
Bio 19	Precipitation of the coldest quarter	mm

To evaluate the impact of climate change on the future suitability of the FAW pest in East Africa, three Shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP) scenarios were employed. these include SSP1-2.6 which represents an optimistic scenario, SSP3-7.0 represents the middle case scenario, and SSP5-8.5 which represents a pessimistic scenario. The three SSPs originating from the CMIP6 project were obtained from two GCMs. These GCMs include the Canadian Earth System Model version 5 (CanESM5) (Swart et al., 2019) and the Institute for Numerical Mathematics- Climate Model 5 (INM-CM5-0) (Volodin et al., 2019). Periods of 20 years for near-term (2021-2040), mid-term (2041-2060) and long-term (2061-2080) were used in this study. All climate data were obtained at a 30-second resolution (~ 1 km).

Modeling procedure

MaxEnt (Phillips et al., 2017) was used to model the current and predict future suitable habitat distribution for FAW in East Africa. MaxEnt has an advantage over other SDMs due to its high accuracy and ability to perform well with small sample sizes (Phillips et al., 2006). We accessed the MaxEnt model in Rstudio (R version 4.2.2 Development Core Team, 2022). Maxent has a built-in function called Jackknife that analyzes the environmental variables' contribution to the

model, displaying the influence of the variable on the FAW distribution. The Maxent output was then predicted to map the suitable habitat of the FAW in our region of interest. The Maxent model output was exported as a tiff file and then imported into ArcGIS 10.4 (<https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/>), a mapping software for further analysis and visualization. The analysis in ArcGIS consisted of reclassification of the Maxent output using the classification package. Taking reference from (Qin et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2013), 10 classes were generated to represent FAW suitability classes. 0-0.1 (unsuitable), 0.1-0.2 (low suitable lower), 0.2-0.3 (low suitable middle), 0.3-0.4 (low suitable upper), 0.4-0.5 (moderate suitable lower), 0.5-0.6 (moderate suitable upper), 0.6-0.7 (good suitable lower), 0.7-0.8 (good suitable upper), 0.8-0.9 (highly suitable lower) and 0.9-1 (highly suitable upper).

Model Evaluation

Model validation is a crucial stage in the modeling process to ensure that the model results are accurate. To test the accuracy of the Maxent model, our data set was split into training (80%) and test (20%) data set. The 80% data set was used to calibrate the model and the remaining 20% was used to validate the model. In this study, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) threshold, a value of the Relative Operating Characteristics (ROC) was used to estimate the accuracy of the model. AUC values of 0.5-0.7 are considered low and represent poor model performance. Values of 0.7 - 0.9 are considered moderate, while values above 0.9 represent excellent model performance. The more the ROC curve follows the y-axis and the larger the AUC, the more the model is considered to be accurate (Bowers & Zhou, 2019).

Results

Maxent model performance

After calibrating the Maxent model with the 80% training dataset and all 19 bioclim variables, the model evaluation output using the 20% test dataset produced a high AUC value of 0.942 (Figure 1). This output, therefore, allowed us to use the Maxent model for other downstream projections in this study.

Figure 1. ROC plot of the Maxent model evaluation results

Bioclimatic variables contribution to FAW suitability

The Maxent built-in Jackknife test results obtained as a quantitative output from the calibration run of the 80% training dataset depict how each of the bioclim variables contributes to the model's performance (Figure 2). We found that of the 19 bioclimatic variables, bio12 (annual precipitation) contributed the most to the performance (37.8%). This depicts the tune to which annual precipitation as a climate variable impacts the model's performance. The second highest contributor was bio1 (annual mean temperature) with a contribution of 13%. This was followed by bio14 (precipitation of the driest month), bio18 (precipitation of the warmest quarter), and bio15 (precipitation seasonality). They contributed 9%, 8.1%, and 7.9%, respectively to the performance of the model.

Figure 2. Bioclimatic variable's contribution to the maxent model

Current FAW suitable habitats in East Africa

The FAW suitability map under the current climatic conditions (1970-2000) in East Africa, (Figure 4) has a large coverage of unsuitable to most suitable habitats for FAW with a minute coverage of the highly suitable class (0.9 - 1). This highly suitable class (black and red) can be seen in the northeastern part of Tanzania, on its border with Kenya (in the black circle). Areas that are still unsuitable for FAW are found in the northern parts of Sudan. In contrast, suitable classes are found in a large part of western to central Ethiopia, and along the borders of Kenya/Tanzania, Kenya/Uganda, and the eastern corridors of Rwanda and Burundi.

Figure 3. Map showing the distribution of FAW cleaned occurrence records. Occurrence records were obtained from FAO, CABI, and Niassy et al., (2021)

Figure 4. Current suitable habitat for FAW in the eastern African region. The zone with the highly suitable area is highlighted with a black circle

Future suitable habitat for FAW for the SSP1-2.6 scenario

Our results show a decline in FAW suitability habitats in the southern parts of East Africa, whereas, in the northern parts of the region, occupied by Sudan, there was the appearance of new suitable habitats. Even Ethiopia, which had the most coverage in good suitable habitats in the current climatic conditions, was losing most of the upper limits of its good suitable habitat. With the two models, we found a visible difference in their projections with INM-CM5-0 projecting zones of high suitability in southwestern Kenya and southern Eritrea, while with CanESM5, these zones are projects more similar suitable class as in the current climatic conditions.

Figure 5. FAW suitable habitat in the SSP1-2.6 scenario based on CanESM5 and INM-CM5-0 global circulation models: for (A) near term 2021-2040, (B) mid-term 2041-2060, and (C) long term 2061-2080

Future suitable habitat for FAW for the SSP3-7.0 scenario

The reduced habitat suitability in the southern parts of East Africa is still observed in this scenario. In contrast, north of East Africa, Sudan's central to western areas will experience increased suitability to FAW, in CanESM5 parts of the country reaching the lower limit of the high suitability habitat in the long term. INM-CM5-0 projects a more northward expansion of FAW suitability. The suitable habitats will continue to decline, as well as the zones along the boundaries of South

Sudan/Sudan, at least in the long term, as projected by both GCMs. Also, both GCMs project a decline of FAW suitability across the period in southern Uganda, and western Tanzania.

Figure 6. FAW suitable habitat in the SSP3-7.0 scenario based on CanESM5 and INM-CM5-0 global circulation models: for (A) near term 2021-2040, (B) mid-term 2041-2060, and (C) long term 2061-2080

Future suitable habitat for FAW for the 5-8.5 scenario

While the southern parts of East Africa, specifically Tanzania and Uganda will continue to become less suitable to FAW, in the north represented by Sudan, parts of the country (central-west and north) will continue to experience both an increase and intensification of its suitable habitats. In CanESM5, the lower limit of the highly suitable habitat is projected to a large extent in this region, this will even reach the upper limit of the highly suitable class in the long term. INM-CM5-0

projects loss and unsuitable habitat in the area, however, projects a lower limit of the highly suitable habitat in areas in central Ethiopia and southern Eritrea.

Figure 7. FAW suitable habitat in the SSP5-8.5 scenario based on CanESM5 and INM-CM5-0 global circulation models: for (A) near term 2021-2040, (B) mid-term 2041-2060, and (C) long term 2061-2080

Discussion

Our results in Figure 2 of the climate variables' contribution to the model show that more than 75% of the Maxent model's overall performance was influenced by just five variables, of which four are related to precipitation and one is related to temperature. The variables are the annual precipitation, annual mean temperature, precipitation of the driest month, precipitation of the warmest quarter, and the precipitation seasonality. It can be said that these variables are the major climatic contributors to FAW suitability and distribution in the eastern Africa region. The

remaining variables each contributed less than 5% to the performance of the model. This indicates that these variables have a minimal impact on the suitability of FAW in the Eastern Africa region. This study agrees with Ramasamy et al. (2022) who conducted a global study on the future suitability of FAW, our study implicates annual precipitation and annual mean temperature as the two most important contributors to FAW's distribution. While the percentage contribution of bio12 is slightly comparable between the two studies (~ 37% and ~ 42%), that from bio1 is not. The value (22%) found by Ramasamy et al. (2022) is slightly higher than the percentage contribution of this variable in this study. Zacarias's (2020) study of global FAW suitability instead positioned annual mean temperature (bio1;19.2%), and precipitation of the driest quarter (bio17;17.3%) as the highest bioclim contributors. Bio12 contributed 11.5% in their study. Cokola et al. (2020) projected FAW's current suitable habitat in South Kivu, DRC. Consistent with the above authors, bio12 was the highest contributor. From these studies in which Africa was involved to some extent, we observe the important role of bio12 – annual precipitation in the distribution of FAW. Current studies highlighted that although FAW has a broad habitat niche, it is most likely to be established in regions with similar climate conditions as that of its native habitats (Cokola et al., 2020). High precipitation is important in growth and development (Wu et al., 2019).

This study shows that in the current climate conditions (Figure 4), FAW suitability is more concentrated in Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, southwestern Kenya, regions in central and northern Tanzania, central to northern Ethiopia, and southern Eritrea. This study also shows that in the future (

Figure 5, Figure 6, and Figure 7) the northern parts of East Africa region will become a hotspot for FAW, while the southern parts will become cold spots. Such a northward shift in FAW's suitability habitat has been highlighted before (Zacarias, 2022). This was observed in the latter authors' FAW suitability study, using the previous CMIP5 scenario. Similarly, to this study, they also found increased suitability in habitat in parts of Sudan, and decline or no changes in suitability habitats in Ethiopia, Tanzania, Kenya, and other parts of East Africa. Similar findings have also been recently projected by Ramasamy et al. (2022) on this strong northward shift in habitat suitability for FAW. However, they found an expansion in suitable areas south of Sudan and in parts of Ethiopia, that spread throughout the country, which was not the case in this study. This was also even though these latter authors used the new CMIP6 scenarios, although different GCMs.

Irrespective of these reduced suitable habitats found in this study, the region will continue to remain suitable for year-round FAW population establishment (Timilsena et al., 2022).

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